

1 **Centenarian hippocampus displays high levels of astrocytic methallothioneins**
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35 **ABSTRACT**

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37 The hippocampus is a brain area linked to cognition. The mechanisms that maintain cognitive activity
38 in humans are poorly understood. Centenarians display extreme longevity which is generally
39 accompanied by better cognitive function and quality of life. We performed transcriptomic studies in
40 hippocampus samples from individuals of different ages (centenarians, elderly and young) and
41 identified a differential gene expression pattern in centenarians compared to the other two groups. In
42 particular, several isoforms of metallothioneins (MTs) were highly expressed in centenarians.
43 Moreover, we identified that MTs were mainly expressed in astrocytes. Functional studies in human
44 primary astrocytes revealed that MT1 and MT3 are necessary for their activity and maintenance.
45 Overall, these results indicate that the expression of MTs specifically in astrocytes is a mechanism for
46 protection during aging.

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51 INTRODUCTION

52 Aging is a systemic, multifactorial, and degenerative process characterized by the decline and loss of
53 physical and mental capacities (1). Although human aging affects the entire organism, brain aging is
54 especially distinctive (2). The brain is probably the most structurally and functionally complex organ
55 which commands multiple cognitive abilities including communication, thinking, memory, movement,
56 and emotions (3). All of them suffer a functional decline with aging until they reach a point in which
57 the individual is not able to perform the activities of daily living (4). Cognitive activities are regulated
58 in part by the 2 neurogenic niches, the subgranular zone of the dentate gyrus (DG) in the hippocampus,
59 that is vital for learning and memory and the subventricular zone (5).

60 Human brain contains billions of neurons, which are surrounded by a vast number of glial cells, whose
61 presence in the brain, compared to the neuron number, is equivalent or even greater in some brain
62 regions (6). The main glial cells from central nervous system (CNS) include macroglia (astrocytes,
63 oligodendrocytes and ependymal cells) and microglia, all of them contributing and regulating different
64 processes such as the correct neurotransmission, neural damage repair, metabolism, blood flow to the
65 brain or even adult neurogenesis (7). The changes that occur in the brain with aging include alterations
66 in the structure and function of neurons, loss of synapses or dysfunctions in neuronal networks (8).
67 Besides neurons, glial cells are also affected by brain aging, losing their ability to carry out their normal
68 functions and releasing detrimental factors which can affect other cells of the brain (9). These alterations
69 in the hippocampus promote a decline in cognitive abilities and the onset of dementia (10). Thus, it is
70 vital to understand how age impacts cognitive function at cellular and molecular level.

71 Previous studies of the aging human brain have shown dynamic gene expression changes that
72 distinguish young adults from the aging population (11). Independent transcriptome analyses have
73 indicated that inflammatory or immune-responsive genes are upregulated during aging in most brain
74 regions (12-14), increasing the vulnerability of the brain to cognitive aging (15). A recent transcriptomic
75 study performed in frontal cortex samples of individuals organized in 2 different groups according to
76 their age (≤ 80 versus ≥ 85 years) showed that the ≥ 85 years group of age was associated with a distinct
77 transcriptome signature in the cerebral cortex and revealed a protective mechanism of aging and
78 longevity mediated by neural circuit activity and regulated by REST transcription factor (16). Similarly,
79 Omic approaches in blood samples from centenarians revealed that the transcriptome and the expression
80 pattern of non-coding RNAs is more similar to young individuals than septuagenarians (17, 18).
81 Moreover, their blood samples overexpress pluripotency and stemness-related genes (19) and show
82 reduced expression of senescence markers when compared to elderly (20), overall supporting the idea
83 that centenarians and very old individuals differ from the elderly and resemble young individuals at
84 biological and molecular level. In this sense, centenarians are a group that exhibits extreme longevity
85 which is commonly accompanied by better cognitive function (21, 22). Additionally, they exhibit
86 medical histories with low incidence rates of age-associated common pathologies, such as dementia and
87 neurodegenerative diseases (23). Thus, in order to understand the mechanisms associated with cognitive

88 decline with aging, we performed transcriptomic analysis in hippocampus samples of human
89 individuals of different ages, including young, elderly and centenarians.

90

91

92 MATERIAL AND METHODS

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94 Human brain samples and public available datasets

95 Individuals included in the study showed the absence of diagnosis of neurodegenerative disorders as
96 well as the lack of neuropathological injuries in the regions analyzed. The transcriptomic study was
97 performed in human hippocampal samples from 16 individuals including young individuals (n = 5, 27
98 to 49 years old), elderly (n = 8, 58 to 88 years old) and very old and centenarians (n = 3, 97 to 100 years
99 old) from the Basque Biobank. Validation was completed in a cohort of 33 individuals including young
100 (n = 16, 27 to 45 years old), elderly (n = 13, 76 to 82) and very old people (n = 4, 92 to 96).
101 Immunofluorescence (IF) studies were completed in paraffin sections from an additional cohort from
102 Pamplona Biobank of 23 individuals including young (n = 7, 26 to 43 years), elderly (n = 14, 65 to 80)
103 and very old (n = 2, 90 and 103). Additionally, Single cell RNAseq data from the brain was analyzed
104 from “The Human Protein Atlas” (<http://www.proteinatlas.org>) using the consensus dataset consisting
105 on the normalized expression (nTPM) levels and RNAseq data of progenitor and mature human
106 astrocytes from (24) (available at <http://www.brainrnaseq.org>). RNAseq data originated from the bulk
107 human dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (n = 540) and purified human microglia (n = 10) from the same
108 brain region were also analyzed (<http://shiny.maths.usyd.edu.au/Ellis/MicrogliaPlots/>). *In situ*
109 hybridization data were obtained from sagittal sections of P56 male adult C57BL/6J mice from Allen
110 Brain Atlas data portal (<https://mouse.brain-map.org/>).

111 Transcriptome analysis

112 Gene expression array was performed from 5 ng of RNA using Clariom™ S array (Affymetrix). Data
113 were normalized using the Robust Multi-array Average (RMA). Then, studied groups were compared
114 with Limma differential expression analysis to find differentially expressed genes. Differentially
115 expressed genes with $p < 0.05$ and fold change $\geq |2|$ were selected. Gene Ontology (GO) analysis was
116 performed using clusterProfiler package in RStudio software (version 4.2.1, [https://www.R-](https://www.R-project.org/)
117 [project.org/](https://www.R-project.org/)) using the differentially expressed genes obtained after the comparisons of centenarians
118 with the other 2 groups. The data discussed in this publication have been deposited in NCBI's Gene
119 Expression Omnibus and are accessible in GSE201118.

120 Astrocytes culture

121 Normal Human Astrocytes (NHA, ScienCell) were cultured in adhesion in culture plates pre-treated
122 with 15 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ poly-L-lysine. Astrocyte medium kit was employed and cells were maintained in
123 standard culture conditions, at 37 °C, 95 % humidity, 21 % O₂ and under 5 % CO₂ pressure. NHA were
124 maintained in culture and passages were performed every 4-5 days. The expression of genes was studied
125 at early (2 - 3) and late (15 - 17) passages after total RNA extraction from cell cultures.

126 Generation of astrocytes from human pluripotent stem cell (hiPSC) lines. hPSCs from the H9 (WA09)
127 line (WiCell Research Institute) maintained on Matrigel in mTeSR1 (StemCell Technologies) were
128 differentiated to neural progenitor cells (NPCs) by dual SMAD inhibition (0.1 μM LDN193189 and

129 10 μ M SB431542) in embryoid bodies (EB) media (StemCell Technologies). Rosettes were selected at
130 DIV 14 by Rosette Selection Reagent and patterned to forebrain NPCs with EB media containing
131 20ng/ml FGF2. NPCs from the H9 line and from the ax0019 line purchased from Axol Bioscience were
132 characterized immunocytochemically using SOX2, PAX6 and Nestin. Dissociated NPCs were plated at
133 a density of 50.000 cells/cm² on matrigel coated plates and differentiated to astrocytes. Briefly, cells
134 were cultured in astrocyte medium (DMEM/F-12 + Glutamax, N2 supplement and B27 supplement
135 without vitamin A) supplemented with EGF and LIF for 14 days and subsequent maturation of
136 astrocytes was obtained by exposure to astrocyte medium supplemented with CNTF for other 30 days.
137 Cells were cultured and harvested at DIV 53-62 and DIV 104-110.

138 **Lentiviral infections**

139 NHA were transduced with lentiviral vectors containing a plasmid with silencing sequence of MT1 or
140 MT3 (Sigma-Aldrich). pLKO.1 puro (Addgene plasmid #8453) was used as control. Lentiviral
141 infections were performed overnight with a multicity of infection (MOI) of 10 at 37 °C and 5 % CO₂
142 in astrocyte medium. After 48 h, infected cells were selected in the presence of 2 μ g/mL puromycin
143 (Sigma-Aldrich) for 48-72 h.

144 **Cell growth and senescence assays**

145 NHA were plated in a density of 10⁴ cells in 6-well plates and number of cells determined at days 1, 4
146 and 8. Data were represented indicating the total number of cells per experimental condition in each
147 time point. Senescence assay was performed using the Senescence β -Galactosidase Staining Kit (Cell
148 Signaling) according to the manufacturer's guidelines.

149 **Cell and tissue IF**

150 Cell IF was performed as described in previous studies (25). Cells were incubated with primary
151 phospho-histone H3 (p-H3) (Abcam), Ki67 (Abcam) and Caspase 3 (R&D Systems) antibodies and
152 secondary anti-mouse and anti-rabbit (Invitrogen) antibodies. For nuclear DNA staining, Hoechst
153 33342 (Sigma) was used. Pictures were taken with an Eclipse 80i microscope and processed with the
154 NIS Elements Advances Research software (Nikon).

155 Tissue IF was performed in formalin fixed brain samples. The sections were deparaffinized and
156 incubated with 0.5 % sodium borohydride for 30 min and heated in citrate buffer at pH6 for 20 min for
157 antigen retrieval. The sections were permeabilized and blocked for 2 h with 2 % normal donkey serum
158 in PBS 0.2 % Triton X-100 and they were incubated at 4 °C overnight with MT1 (Abcam), MT3
159 (Sigma), GFAP (Invitrogen), S100 β (Abcam), MAP2 (Sigma), TUJ1 (Biolegend) primary antibodies.
160 Nuclear DNA was stained with 10 mg/mL DAPI (40043, Biotium) for 20 min. Finally, sections were
161 submerged in 70 % ethanol for 5 min and incubated with autofluorescence eliminator reagent for
162 background removal. The preparation was mounted with ProlongTM Gold antifade mounting media
163 (Invitrogen) and IF was evaluated with SP5 laser scanning confocal microscope (TCS SP5, Leica).
164 Processing and analysis were performed on the maximal intensity projection of the z-stack using Fiji

165 software. Quantification was measured based on each protein positive signal percentage respect to total
166 nuclei in DAPI channel.

167 **RNA extraction and analysis by quantitative real-time PCR**

168 Total RNA extraction was performed by Trizol (Life Technologies). Reverse transcription was
169 performed using random priming and Maxima First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (Thermo Fisher). To
170 analyze gene expression, quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR) with 20 ng of
171 cDNA was performed by Absolute SYBR Green mix (Thermo Scientific) on a CFX384 thermal cyclor
172 (Bio-Rad). Transcript levels were normalized to Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase
173 (GAPDH) and measured using the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ relative quantification method.

174 **Western blot analysis**

175 Immunoblots were performed following standard procedures. Specific antibodies against MT1
176 (Abcam), MT3 (Sigma) and β -actin (Sigma-Aldrich) were used in the study. Detection was performed
177 by chemiluminescence using NOVEX ECL Chemi Substrate and SuperSignal™ West Femto Maximum
178 Sensitivity Substrate (ThermoFisher).

179 **Data analysis**

180 Statistical analyses and graphics were performed using Microsoft Office Excel, IBM SPSS Statistics 20
181 and GraphPad Prism 8 software. Data are represented as mean values \pm SEM, with the number of
182 experiments (n) carried out for each assay. Unless otherwise indicated, statistical significance was
183 calculated by Student's t-test ($\neq p < 0.1$, $*p \leq 0.05$; $**p \leq 0.01$; $***p \leq 0.001$). For correlation analysis,
184 we first performed a Kolmogorov Smirnov test for the assessment of normality and then we used
185 Pearson's coefficient when samples were normally distributed or Spearman's coefficient when they were
186 not normally distributed.

187 **Ethics approval**

188 This study was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of the Donostia University
189 Hospital (protocol AMF-EGM-2016-01) and adhered to the tenets of the Declaration of Helsinki.

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191

192 **RESULTS**

193 ***Transcriptome analysis reveal differential gene expression pattern in centenarian hippocampus.***

194 Transcriptome analysis in hippocampus from individuals of different ages showed a differential gene
195 expression pattern in centenarians compared to elderly (**Fig 1A**) and young individuals (**Fig 1B**). In
196 particular, 255 genes were differentially expressed in centenarians compared to elderly among which
197 190 were increased and 65 reduced (**Suppl Table 1-2**). Moreover, 209 genes were differentially
198 expressed in centenarians relative to young ones (**Fig 1C**) among which 135 were higher and 74
199 decreased (**Suppl Table 3-4**). GO analysis revealed heavy metal related biological processes associated
200 to up-regulated genes in centenarians when compared to the other two groups (**Fig 1D**). In detail, genes
201 associated to pathways involved in zinc (Zn) homeostasis, detoxification of metals and cellular response
202 to metals were highly enriched (**Fig 1D**). The differentially expressed genes associated with these
203 biological processes included members of the metallothioneins (*MTs*) family, that were the ones most
204 significantly increased in the hippocampus of centenarians (**Fig 1E and Suppl Fig 1A**). Moreover, the
205 expression of *Transferrin Receptor (TFRC)* and *Solute Carrier Family 39 Member 12 (SLC39A12)* also
206 known as *ZIP12*, were also augmented (**Fig 1E**). *TFRC* is a cell surface receptor necessary for cellular
207 iron uptake by the process of receptor-mediated endocytosis that is required in neurologic development
208 (26) and *ZIP12* is a zinc transporter with an important role in nervous system development, and that its
209 mutations or lower levels have been associated with several brain diseases (27, 28). On the other hand,
210 cell growth or axon extension processes were associated to down-regulated genes in centenarians when
211 compared to the other two groups (**Fig 1F and Suppl Fig 1B**).

212

213 ***MTs are highly expressed in the hippocampus of very old individuals.***

214 We further characterized *MTs* expression in hippocampus samples from 2 additional cohorts at mRNA
215 and protein levels. In the first case, higher expression levels of mRNA of multiple *MT1* isoforms were
216 detected in very old individuals (over 90 years old) compared to young and elderly individuals.
217 Specifically, very old brain samples displayed a 2-fold increase of *MT1A*, *MT1E*, *MT1F*, *MT1G*, *MT1H*,
218 *MT1M* and *MT1X* compared to young or elderly (**Fig 2A**). Similarly, the brain-specific *MT3* isoform
219 was significantly increased in very old individuals (**Fig 2B**). Additionally, expression of *REST*, which
220 has been described as an important player of extreme longevity and cognitive activity (16), was elevated
221 in hippocampus samples of very old individuals (**Fig 2C**). In order to study the possibility of brain
222 region specificity, the expression of different *MTs* subtypes was measured in cortex samples of
223 individuals from the transcriptome analysis and we did not detect significant changes in *MT* levels
224 within very old and elderly (**Suppl Fig 2A**). Consistent with the relevance of *MTs* in hippocampus,
225 Allen Mouse Brain Atlas (<https://mouse.brain-map.org/>) shows enrichment of *MT1* and *MT3*
226 expression in hippocampus (particularly in the DG) (**Suppl Fig 2B**), and immunohistochemistry (IHC)
227 revealed *MT* staining in the different regions of the human hippocampus (**Fig 2D**). IF analysis of DG
228 in very old individuals also revealed significantly higher protein expression of *MT1* and *MT3* compared

229 to the other two groups (**Fig 2E-H**). An additional analysis was performed to identify a possible
230 correlation between MTs expression with age in the hippocampus samples from the 2 validation
231 cohorts. Herein, we found that the expression of different *MT1* isoforms and *MT3* (**Suppl Fig 2C-D**)
232 correlated positively with age at mRNA level. However, there was not statistically significant
233 correlation between MT1/MT3 protein levels with age of individuals (**Suppl Fig 2E**). These results
234 confirm that MTs are highly expressed in the hippocampus of very old individuals.

235

236 ***MTs are mainly expressed by astrocytes.***

237 In order to take a further step in the characterization of the expression of MTs, we studied their
238 expression in different brain cell types. For this, we first analyzed single cell RNAseq studies performed
239 in human brains from The Human Protein Atlas (<http://www.proteinatlas.org>). In this case, we observed
240 that the different isoforms of *MT1* and *MT3* were expressed almost exclusively by astrocytes (**Fig 3A-**
241 **B**). An additional RNAseq study of human astrocytes compared to other cell types of the brain (24)
242 showed similar results (**Suppl Fig 3A-B**). In line with this, IHC in human hippocampus samples
243 indicated positive staining of MT3 in astrocytes (**Fig 3C**). To further study the link of *MTs* with
244 astrocytes, co-IF of both *MT1* and *MT3* with glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) and S100 calcium-
245 binding protein β (S100 β) were completed. These analyses revealed that on average 80-85 % of the
246 cells positive for *MT1* or *MT3* were also positive for GFAP (**Fig 3D-G**). In the same line, co-staining
247 of *MT1* or *MT3* with S100 β showed that 95 % of MT positive cells were also positive for the astrocytic
248 marker (**Fig 4H-K**). These results were obtained in the different groups of age, young, elderly and very
249 old. Next, we further characterized expression in different cell types and performed co-staining studies
250 of *MT1* and *MT3* with markers of neurons. Co-IF of both *MT1* and *MT3* with microtubule-associated
251 protein 2 (MAP2) and Class III β -Tubulin (TUJ1) neuronal markers revealed that around 5% of the
252 cells that were positive for *MT1* or *MT3* were also positive for MAP2 (**Suppl Fig 4A-D**) or TUJ1 (**Suppl**
253 **Fig 4E-H**), independently of the age of the cases. We also checked their expression in microglia taking
254 advantage of RNAseq data from aged human bulk dorsolateral prefrontal cortex samples and purified
255 microglia from the same region (<http://shiny.maths.usyd.edu.au/Ellis/MicrogliaPlots/>). This analysis
256 showed that none of the *MT1s* or *MT3* were enriched in microglia compared to bulk cortex (**Suppl Fig**
257 **4I-J**). Together, these results reveal that astrocytes express high levels of MTs.

258

259 ***MTs expression decrease in cultured astrocytes.***

260 Since MTs are mainly expressed in astrocytes, we further characterized the expression of MTs
261 specifically in human astrocytes performing *in vitro* experiments. First, we measured their expression
262 in astrocytes derived from hiPSC at two stages: as progenitors (DIV53-62) and as mature astrocytes
263 (DIV104-110). This comparison showed a reduction in GFAP staining by IF analysis (**Fig 4A-B**), which
264 correlated with lower *MT1* and *MT3* protein levels in mature astrocytes at \cong DIV110 compared to \cong
265 DIV60 progenitors (**Fig 4C-E**). Co-IF confirmed the co-staining of *MT1* and *MT3* with GFAP further

266 linking MTs expression to astrocytes (**Fig 4F**). Quantitative RT-PCR analysis further revealed a
267 significant decrease of over 2.5-fold in mRNA expression of all *MT1* isoforms and *MT3* in mature
268 astrocytes after 110 days in culture (**Fig 4G**). We also compared the expression of *MTs* in NHA (human
269 primary astrocytes) at early and late passages. In the case of *MT1* subtypes, the expression was
270 decreased in the majority of cases in late passage NHA being statistically significant for *MT1A*, *MT1E*,
271 *MT1F* and *MT1X* (**Fig 4H**). Similarly, the levels of *MT3* were also lower in late passage NHA (**Fig**
272 **4H**), whereas the markers of senescence and aging *p16^{INK4A}*, *p21^{CIP1}* and *IL6* were increased (**Fig 4I**).
273 These results indicate that astrocytes maintained in culture for longer periods have lower levels of *MTs*.
274

275 ***MT1 and MT3 silencing impairs astrocytic viability and activity.***

276 We finally studied the possible effects of the modulation of *MTs* in NHA cells in order to unravel the
277 possible role that *MTs* might have in astrocytes. For this, we independently silenced *MT1* and *MT3* in
278 astrocytes using lentiviral infections and specific shRNA constructs for each gene. Western blot and IF
279 revealed statistically significant lower protein levels and reduced number of cells expressing *MT1* and
280 *MT3* in NHA with *MT1* or *MT3* downregulation (*shMT1* or *shMT3*) compared to control ones (*pLKO*)
281 (**Fig 5A-B and Suppl Fig 5A**). In line with this, mRNA expression of all *MT1* subtypes and *MT3* was
282 lower in *shMT1* and *shMT3* astrocytes, respectively (**Fig 5C-D**). Consequently, we performed different
283 functional assays in order to analyze the cellular effects of *MT1* or *MT3* silencing. First, cell growth
284 study revealed that *MT*-silenced NHA cells displayed different growth kinetics with lower cell numbers
285 in *shMT1* or *shMT3* compared to control astrocytes measured by cell counting (**Suppl Fig 5B**). In line
286 with this result, staining of Ki67 proliferation marker showed significantly reduced positive cells in
287 *shMT1* and *shMT3* (from 20% in controls to less than 3% in *shMT* cells) (**Fig 5E and Suppl Fig 5C**).
288 Furthermore, silencing of *MTs* significantly increased apoptosis measured as the number of positive
289 cells for Caspase 3 marker (**Fig 5F and Suppl Fig 5D**). Finally, we also measured the effect of *MTs*
290 silencing in cellular senescence, detecting a significantly higher number of SA- β -galactosidase positive
291 cells in *shMT* cultures (**Fig 5G and Suppl Fig 5E**), as well as higher levels of *p21^{CIP1}*, cell cycle arrest
292 and senescence marker, and *IL6*, SASP and inflammation marker (**Fig 5H-I**). In summary, these results
293 reveal that *MT1* and *MT3* have a role in astrocyte viability and activity.

294 Reactive astrocytes are activated in response to physiological and pathological states that causes
295 morphological, molecular, and functional remodeling (29). Astrocyte reactivity is heterogenous and
296 two main subtypes has been proposed. Neuroprotective phenotype related to the promotion of synaptic
297 formation, growth of neurites and production of anti-inflammatory factors and cytotoxic or
298 inflammatory that lead to cellular damage, and it associated to aging, neurodegeneration and disease.
299 Based on this, we measured the expression of several pro-inflammatory markers such as *TNF α* , *IL1 α* ,
300 and *C3*, linked to cytotoxic subtype. All the markers were elevated at mRNA level in both *shMT1* and
301 *shMT3* NHAs in comparison to control ones (**Fig 5H-I**). In order to further characterize the impact of
302 *MTs* blockage, we studied the comprehensive profile of cytokines secreted by *shMT1* and *shMT3* NHA.

303 For this, we performed a cytokine expression array from supernatants of control and *MTs* silenced cells.
304 Interestingly, this study showed deregulated cytokines in both *MT* silencing cells with several cytokines
305 and chemokines related to inflammatory subtype of astrocytes (*Suppl Fig 5F-G*). Interestingly, 8 were
306 altered in both conditions (*Fig 5J*). Notably, secretion of IL1 α , GRO (CXCL1), ENA78 (CXCL5),
307 SDF1 (CXCL12), IL10, and TGF β 1 was increased in *shMT* compared to control cells (*Fig 5K*). These
308 results suggest that astrocytes with *MT* silencing behave as cytotoxic ones.
309

310 **DISCUSSION**

311 We have performed a transcriptomic analysis in hippocampus samples of individuals of different ages
312 detecting a differential expression pattern in centenarians compared to young and elderly groups.
313 Notably, heavy metal in general and Zn related pathways, in particular, were GO terms enriched among
314 differentially expressed transcripts in centenarians. There is a link between Zn levels in the brain and
315 cognitive function, and the decline in cognitive performance observed during aging or the apparition of
316 neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease (AD), has been linked to the dysregulation of
317 Zn homeostasis (30). For instance, reduced zinc transporter-3 (*ZnT3*) expression or mutations of this
318 gene, which is responsible for loading zinc into presynaptic vesicles in the hippocampus (31), have been
319 associated to the onset of cognitive decline and accelerated brain aging, ultimately impairing learning
320 and memory functions (32-34). Additional metals such as iron and Cu, are also involved in brain aging
321 since they trigger oxidative stress, accumulation of damaging molecules, DNA damage and
322 neuroinflammation (35, 36).

323 The concentration of Zn in the brain surpasses that of the body by ten-fold and it is essential for its
324 normal functioning (37). It is tightly controlled and it plays an important role in cellular and molecular
325 processes, enzymatic activity and regulation of transcription factors (38). In the brain, the majority of
326 Zn tightly binds to macromolecules such as proteins or amino acids and only 10 to 15 % exist as free
327 Zn (38). *MTs*, Zn transporters family (*ZnTs*), presenilins, and zinc-regulated and iron-regulated proteins
328 (*ZIPs*) are responsible for the homeostasis of Zn in the brain (39, 40). Among the differentially
329 expressed genes, several members of the *MTs* family of genes were highly expressed in the
330 hippocampus of very old individuals. *MTs* are a family of cysteine-rich proteins involved in the
331 homeostasis and detoxification of heavy metals, specifically they bind divalent metals such as Zn and
332 Cu (41, 42). Different *MTI* subtypes have been described which are found ubiquitously in a broad range
333 of organs, in contrast to *MT3*, which is a brain-specific isoform (43, 44). They are not limited to the
334 homeostasis or detoxification of heavy metals, and they have been described as having cytoprotective
335 effects that promote cell survival and tissue regeneration. Indeed, they have been reported as anti-
336 inflammatory and anti-oxidants, with a role in the protection against oxidative stress, apoptosis and
337 DNA damage (45-48). A European study focused on aging (MARK-AGE project), showed that PBMCs
338 from centenarian´s offspring displayed increased basal expression of some *MTs* and *Zinc transporter 1*
339 genes in comparison to the general population (49). In addition, *MTs* levels were found to be inversely
340 related with oxidative stress markers (49). Moreover, an additional study performed in Italian
341 centenarian females showed that a specific SNP corresponding to an Adenine/Cytosine
342 (Asparagine/Threonine) transition at +647 nucleotide position in the *MT1A* coding region is associated
343 with longevity, since it was present in nonagenarian and centenarian females (50). In addition, it was
344 associated with lower inflammatory status, since lower levels of circulating IL6 in plasma of these
345 individuals was observed (50). Our results, together with these ones, indicate that centenarians and their

346 offspring have enrichment of MTs and a better control of Zn homeostasis that provides them protection
347 against stress stimuli over the whole lifespan.

348 The results obtained in our study are further supported by studies in mouse models. Thus, a study
349 performed in *Mt1/Mt2*-null mice reported that *MTs* mutants showed a poorer rate of learning and
350 memory (51). Additionally, studies performed in *Mt1* or *Mt3*-null mice models described that MTs have
351 a role in CNS homeostasis, since they are induced in the aging brain as a defensive mechanism to
352 attenuate oxidative stress, ROS production and inflammation (52, 53). Indeed, after damage caused by
353 a focal cryolesion in the cortex, mice with deletions of *MTs* showed increased oxidative stress,
354 apoptosis, astrogliosis and secretion of several inflammatory cytokines including TNF α , IL1 α , IL6 (52).
355 Moreover, the protective role of high levels of MTs in aging and longevity has been documented in
356 different animal models. Thus, several studies have indicated that high levels of MTs prevent diabetic
357 complications (54), attenuate cardiac dysfunction (55), protect against organ damages during
358 inflammation (56), and against DNA and lipid metabolic damages (57). Regarding longevity, *Mt1*-
359 overexpressing mice model displayed increased lifespan (58). Consistently, cardiac-specific *MT*
360 transgenic mice, also presented increased longevity together with an attenuation of oxidative stress (59).
361 By contrast, *Mt1* knockout mice displayed shorter lifespan than wild type mice (60).

362 Co-staining studies of *MT1* and *MT3* with markers of specific cell types of the brain, single cell
363 RNAseq from The Human Protein Atlas (<http://www.proteinatlas.org>) and RNAseq study of progenitor
364 and mature human astrocytes (24) revealed that MTs were expressed mainly by astrocytes. Moreover,
365 MTs levels in astrocytes derived from human pluripotent stem cell lines was lower in mature astrocytes
366 compared to progenitors. Physiological aging triggers astrocyte activation in order to respond to stress
367 signals and astrocyte dysfunction contribute to cognitive decline in aging (61). We found that old or
368 late passage cultured astrocytes presented lower levels of MTs and that silencing of *MT1* or *MT3* in
369 NHA, resulted in (i) decreased proliferation and (ii) increased apoptosis and senescence, indicating that
370 MTs are involved in astrocyte cell viability and activity. These results are in agreement with other
371 studies performed in mouse models where the upregulation of *Mt3* in glial cells provided
372 neuroprotective effect after brain damage acting as a growth inhibitory factor (62). Moreover, studies
373 performed in *Mt1* transgenic mice, have shown that *Mt1* is expressed in response to brain damage and
374 protect the CNS (51). In addition, mice overexpressing *Mt1* were protected against mild focal cerebral
375 ischemia, showing fewer infarcts and better functional recovery than the controls (63) and the opposite
376 was observed in null mice (64). In line with these results, MTs deficiency increases oxidative stress and
377 cell death, worsening recovery in traumatic injuries or in neurodegenerative pathologies (65-68). For
378 instance, the downregulation of *MT3* has been associated with AD, since silencing of *MT3* in cortical
379 astrocytes reduced amyloid beta uptake and contributed to its accumulation (69). In addition, we
380 observed an increase in the expression of inflammatory genes and secreted cytokines after *MTs*
381 silencing that could be linked with reactive phenotype of astrocytes (61). Consistent with our data,
382 additional studies have shown that MTs regulates the expression of inflammatory factors mainly

383 cytokines such as IL6, TNF α and interferons in the brain of mice (70, 71). However, future studies
384 would be necessary to identify whether MTs have a role in astrocyte polarization.

385 As a summary, we detected high levels of MTs in the hippocampus of centenarian individuals.
386 Moreover, MTs are expressed in astrocytes, where we confirmed that they have a role in their viability
387 and activity. Our results suggests that MTs could respond to stress situations and provide protection in
388 the aging brain. Therefore, maintenance of their high levels could be a potential anti-aging and cognitive
389 decline strategy.

390

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400

401 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS:** A.S-A performed the experiments, analyzed the results and wrote the
402 draft of the manuscript. P.R and F.G helped with the IF experiments and supervised experiments within
403 the stay in the Francis Crick Institute. M.M-C, M.M-V, S.C-S, AA and D.O completed the
404 transcriptomic study, the consequent bionformatic analysis and helped with the validations. L.R-B and
405 AM.A performed the experiments with iPSC derived astrocytes and M.A provided brain samples. All
406 of them revised the manuscript. A.M directed the project, obtained funds, contributed to data analysis
407 and wrote of the manuscript.

408

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- 583
- 584

585 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

586

587 **FIGURE 1. Differentially expressed genes in centenarians hippocampus.** (A-B) Hierarchical
588 clustering of centenarian (n = 3) vs elderly (n = 8) and young individuals (n = 5). (C) Number of genes
589 increased and decreased genes in the transcriptomic analysis (p-value < 0.05 and FC ≥ |2|). (D)
590 Representative dotplot after Gene Ontology (GO) analysis associated to increased genes in centenarians
591 vs elderly and young individuals. (E) Statistical significance of the genes associated with biological
592 pathways obtained after GO. (F) Representative dotplot after GO analysis associated to decreased genes
593 in centenarians vs elderly and young individuals.

594

595 **FIGURE 2. MTs are highly expressed in the hippocampus of very old individuals.** (A-B) mRNA
596 levels of indicated MT isoforms in hippocampus samples of young (n ≥ 16), elderly (n ≥ 10) and very
597 old individuals (n ≥ 4) from cohort 1. (C) Expression of *REST* in same samples. (D) Representative
598 immunohistochemistry image of MT3 in human hippocampus. (E-F) Representative
599 immunofluorescence (IF) images of MT1 and MT3 (red) in the DG of young (n = 6), elderly (n = 13)
600 and very old individuals (n = 2) from cohort 2 (scale bar = 50 μm). (G-H) Quantification of MT1 and
601 MT3 protein levels in samples from cohort 2. Figure represents percentage of MT1 or MT3 positive
602 cells respect to nuclei stained with DAPI (blue). The statistical significance was assessed with the
603 Student's t-test (≠ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001).

604

605 **FIGURE 3. MTs are mainly expressed by astrocytes.** (A-B) Normalized expression (nTPM) of *MT1*
606 and *MT3* using Single cell RNAseq data from whole brain from “The Human Protein Atlas”
607 (<http://www.proteinatlas.org>). (C) Immunohistochemistry of MT3 in human DG. (D) Representative
608 immunofluorescence (IF) images of GFAP (green) and MT1 (far red) in the dentate gyrus (DG, scale
609 bar = 50 μm) of hippocampal coronal sections of young (n = 6), elderly (n = 13) and very old individuals
610 (n = 2) from the validation cohort 2. (E) Representative IF images of GFAP (green) MT3 (red) in DG
611 samples of the same cohort (young n = 6, elderly n = 13, very old n = 2; scale bar = 50 μm). (F-G)
612 Quantification (percentage) of MT1 and MT3 positive cells that are also positive for GFAP
613 (MT1+/GFAP+ or MT3+/GFAP+ cells) in the DG of the same samples. (H) Representative IF images
614 of S100β (far red) and MT1 (red) in DG samples from the validation cohort 2 (young n = 3, elderly n =
615 11, very old n = 2; scale bar = 50 μm). (I) Representative IF images of S100β (far red) and MT3 (red)
616 in DG samples of the same cohort (young n = 4, elderly n = 5, very old n = 2; scale bar = 50 μm). (J-
617 K) Quantification (percentage) of MT1 or MT3 positive cells that are also positive for S100β (MT1+/
618 S100β+ or MT3+ /S100β+ cells) in the DG of the same samples.

619

620 **FIGURE 4. MTs expression decrease in cultured astrocytes.** (A-B) Representative
621 immunofluorescence (IF) images and quantification of GFAP expression in hiPSC-derived astrocyte

622 progenitors (day-*in-vitro* 60) and more mature astrocytes (day-*in-vitro* 110). (C) Representative IF
623 images of MT1 and MT3 expression in astrocytes at DIV60 vs DIV110 (n = 3). (D-E) Quantification
624 of the mean intensity of MT1 and MT3 in astrocytes at DIV60 and DIV110 (n = 3). (F) Representative
625 image of GFAP, MT1 and MT3 in astrocytes at DIV60 (n = 3). (G) mRNA levels of *MT* isoforms in
626 astrocytes at DIV53-62 (progenitor) and DIV104-110 (mature). (H) mRNA levels of *MT* isoforms and
627 (I) *p16^{INK4A}*, *p21^{CIP1}*, *IL6* in NHA cultured at early (2-3) and late (15-17) passages (n = 2). The statistical
628 significance was assessed with the Student's t-test ($\neq p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

629

630 **FIGURE 5. *MT1* and *MT3* silencing decrease astrocytic activity.** *MT1* and *MT3* silencing was done
631 in NHA using lentiviral infections. (A) Representative western blot of *MT1* and *MT3* in NHA with
632 *MT1* (*shMT1*) or *MT3* silencing (*shMT3*) compared to controls (*pLKO*) (n = 3). (B) Representative
633 immunofluorescence images of *MT1* and *MT3* in indicated cell types (scale bar = 50 μ m). (C) mRNA
634 levels of *MT1* isoforms in *shMT1* compared to *pLKO* cells (n = 2). (D) *MT3* levels in *shMT3* relative to
635 *pLKO* (n = 3). (E) Quantification of Ki67⁺ cells, (F) Caspase 3⁺ cells and (G) SA- β -gal activity in *MT*
636 silenced compared to *pLKO* NHA (n = 3). (H-I) mRNA levels of *p21^{CIP1}*, *IL6*, *TNF α* , *IL1 α* and *C3* in
637 *shMT1* and *shMT3* astrocytes compared to controls (n = 3). (J) Venn diagram and (K) heat map of the
638 altered secreted common cytokines from supernatants of *shMT1* and *shMT3* NHA compared to *pLKO*
639 astrocytes ($p < 0.05$, n = 2). The statistical significance was assessed with the Student's t-test ($\neq p < 0.1$,
640 * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

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A**E**

DEGs	P-VALUE
<i>MT1M, MT1E, MT1X</i>	≤ 0.0001
<i>MT1F, MT1A</i>	≤ 0.001
<i>MT1G, MT1B, SLC39A12</i>	≤ 0.01
<i>MT3, TFRC</i>	≤ 0.05

F

